

Analysis of antioxidant nutrients, anti-HIV and anticancer metabolic fingerprints of *Pelargonium quercifolium* (L.f) L'Hér

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ABSTRACT

Pelargonium quercifolium is an aromatic herb with a strong resinous scent. It is used traditionally to treat heart disease, hypertension, stress, rheumatism, combat hidden hunger, and inhibit HIV-1. The present study aimed to evaluate the toxicity, anti-HIV, antioxidant nutrients and anticancer potentials of the ethanol extract of *P. quercifolium*. In this study, high-resolution ultra-performance liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (UPLC-MS), high-performance liquid chromatography with diode-array detection (HPLC-D AD), xCELLigence real-time cell analyser single plate (RTCA-SP), MTT assays and luciferase-based assay were employed to elucidate the phytochemicals, cytotoxicity, anti-HIV, antioxidant nutrients and anticancer metabolites in *P. quercifolium*. Results show that the characterized metabolites in *P. quercifolium* most of which were flavonoids, phenolic derivatives, alkaloids and coumarins could arrest cancer cell proliferation and inhibit HIV infection given the high level of cytotoxicity of the tested plant extract. It was also observed and reported for the first time, the nutrient profile of *P. quercifolium* is higher than most vegetables consumed as a staple food. This study underpins the potential of using anticancer and antiviral metabolites from leaf extract of *P. quercifolium* as a pharmacological option.

1. Introduction

The African continent has more plants that have been used for medicinal purposes, including treating and managing viral diseases such as HIV (Iwu, 2014; Prinsloo et al., 2018). Human Immunodeficiency remains a global health challenge, especially in Southern Africa, despite the development of antiretroviral therapy. The HIV-1 virus cannot be completely removed from viral reservoirs by antiretroviral drugs,

although they can inhibit HIV-1 replication and lower the plasma viral load to an undetectable level (Sarzotti-Kelsoe et al., 2014). The emergence of drug-resistance mutations further undermines antiretroviral therapy's success story. Non-communicable diseases continue to be a concern in clinical research, despite the increased emphasis on infectious disorders, particularly among HIV-1-positive individuals (Alexaki et al., 2008). Therefore, research and development into novel, cost-effective therapies for chronic noncommunicable diseases is still

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required. As a result, the search for and development of novel, safe, and efficacious medications that target HIV-1's unique sites is ongoing.

Cancer is one of the leading causes of death worldwide, and the rising cancer-related death rate is drawing attention to the need for effective anticancer treatments. Pharmaceutical research has relied heavily on natural products to create innovative and potent anticancer medications. Plant derivatives include paclitaxel, etoposide (Etoposide), podophyllotoxin, irinotecan, topotecan, vincristine, and vinblastine have played a significant role in producing effective anticancer drugs (Asma et al., 2022). Various other plant-derived bioactive chemicals, like gimatecan and topotecan, are in the clinical development phase against cancer due to their specific action (Asma et al., 2022; Zhu et al., 2009). According to a recent study where *in vitro* and *in silico* methods were used to evaluate the antiviral potential of beneficial bioactive chemicals derived from specific aquatic plants (Das et al., 2023), the *in vitro* research revealed that carrageenan from *Odonthalia floccosa* was cytopathic against both herpes virus type 1 and the polio virus. Similarly, *Zostera maria* produced rosmarinic acid, while *Ipomea aquatica* produced chlorogenic acid. A new novel anti-HIV-1 daphnane-type diterpenoids from *Stellera chamaejasme* L. were previously discovered (Asada et al., 2011). Stelleralide A separated from the roots of *Stellera chamaejasme* L. was tested for anti-HIV-1 activity and cytotoxicity against NL4.3 in MT4 cells. The results showed a very low level of cytotoxicity and high viral suppression with an EC90 of 0.4 nM discovered (Asada et al., 2011).

Biologically active compounds are specialised metabolites of low-molecular-weight synthesised by plants (Tava et al., 2021). They may exist as latent drug principles being activated by certain mechanisms during defense against herbivory, harmful ultraviolet radiation, pathogens, and allelopathy and while adapting to environmental stressors (Jimoh & Kambizi, 2022; Schreiner et al., 2012). The physicochemical properties of these metabolites confer on them various pharmacological potentials such as antioxidant, anticancer, antiviral, anti-feedant properties to antiparasitic, insecticidal, antifungal, antimicrobial, nematocidal and antidepressant effects, with which they lessen the burden of chronic diseases (Idris et al., 2019; Jimoh et al., 2024; Tava et al., 2021). These botanical metabolites have been thought to have a reduced risk of chronic manifestation compared to synthetic drugs (Jimoh & Kambizi, 2022). It has been demonstrated that bioactive compounds derived from natural products are the source of antioxidant and antiviral substances used to treat infectious and non-communicable diseases (Frediansyah et al., 2022).

The use of plants in mitigating disease risk is not new to human existence. Anciently, humans used plants as primary sources of food, drugs and shelter (Kurhekar, 2021). Archaeological records also show how man used psychoactive plants to alter his state of consciousness in ancient dates (Samorini, 2019). Unfortunately, a significant departure from this practice is witnessed in modern times when the health benefits of botanical foods and dietary fibres are often-overlooked (Barron, 2022; Chivenge et al., 2015). In some cases, wild vegetables are considered food for poor and economically vulnerable households (Paumgarten et al., 2018) while their suitability in combating hidden hunger and malnutrition is underestimated (Bvenura & Sivakumar 2017; Jimoh et al., 2018). Over the years, natural intervention, including the application of medicinal plants and consumption of plant-based diets, has been recommended as the most effective panacea for preventing chronic diseases arising from cognitive impairment, cardiovascular complications, metabolic disorders, diabetes and cancer (Barron, 2022; Gemede & Ratta, 2014). These plant-based foods are naturally rich in biologically active compounds like phenolic acids, carotenoids, flavonoids, anthocyanins, antioxidants, lignans, tannins and other essential nutrients that can combat oxidative stress and reinforce the efficiency of the central nervous system (Espín et al., 2000; Jimoh et al., 2020).

One of such important groups of plants capable of mitigating chronic diseases are the *Pelargonium* species belonging to the family Geraniaceae, a family known for its characteristic geranium oil (Lalli et al.,

2019). About 270 *Pelargonium* species exist globally, most of which are native and endemic to Southern Africa, especially the Southwestern Cape (Yousefian et al., 2023). *Pelargonium quercifolium* (L.f) L'Hér. is an evergreen shrub with sticky, strong, balm-scented palmate leaves. Younger stems are herbaceous, with green glandular hairs that turn brown and woody at maturity (Adams, 2009). The inflorescence is umbel-like, bearing pale pink or pinkish purple flowers numbering 2 to 6. Unlike *Pelargonium sidoides* and other Southern African plants which were reported as a strong inhibitor of HIV-1 (Helfer et al., 2014; Prinsloo et al., 2018), little is known about the potential of *P. quercifolium* in inhibiting HIV-1. Organic compounds including gallic acid, umckalin, catechin, oleic acid, linoleic acid, and coumarins that directly affect HIV infectivity and prevent viral attachment are produced by *Pelargonium sidoides* (Helfer et al., 2014). Using the DPPH test, other *Pelargonium* species showed that their leaves and roots had antioxidant activity, suggesting that they might be used to treat liver diseases (Ingarfield et al., 2023; Kolodziej, 2007). Previous studies on *P. quercifolium* had focused on the ornamental values, cultivation and the diverse chemicals in the essential oils extracted from different *Pelargonium* species using the gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) technique (Blerot et al., 2015; Miller, 1996). However, little to no attention is given to non-oil metabolites, especially those that may be characterised with high-resolution liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS) and tested against HIV and cancer-infected cells.

In this study, high-resolution ultra-performance liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (UPLC-MS), high-performance liquid chromatography with diode-array detection (HPLC-D AD), xCELLigence real-time cell analyser single plate (RTCA-SP), and MTT assays were employed to elucidate the cytotoxicity, antioxidant nutrients, anti-HIV and anticancer metabolites in *P. quercifolium* while and luciferase-based assay was used to test its anti-HIV efficacy. The macronutrients and micronutrients in the plant were also analysed using the Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS) following referenced methods. It will be beneficial to elucidate the chemical profiles of metabolites aggregated in crude extracts of *P. quercifolium* using high-resolution UPLC-MS and HPLC-DAD to correlate between the attributed characteristics of indexed chemical compounds in their pure form and the biological activities exhibited by the crude extracts when tested on HIV and cancer infected cells. Therefore, this study analyses the nutritional, antioxidants, anti-cancer and antiviral fingerprints of *P. quercifolium*.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Collection of plant samples and preparation for analysis

Fresh leaves of *P. quercifolium* also known as oak-leaf pelargonium (Eng.) were collected during summer (January 2023), from the Horticultural Garden, Department of Horticultural Science, Cape Peninsula University of Technology, Bellville, South Africa (Fig. 1). The plant was allocated a voucher number 5518 accordingly at the Cape Peninsula University of Technology Herbarium. The plant sample was washed, dried in an oven at 35 °C to a constant weight, and ground to powder. The pulverised plant was refrigerated for further treatments.

2.2. Extraction of plant bioactive compounds

Thirty grams (30 g) of the pulverised *P. quercifolium* leaves were measured on a weighing balance and transferred into a spherical flask filled with 500 mL of 70 % ethanol and shaken briskly with an orbital shaker (Gallenkamp, Cambridge CB4 1TF, United Kingdom) at 120 rpm for 48 h. The extracted mixture was sifted through a Whatman No 1 filter paper placed in a Buchner funnel connected to a vacuum pump, which generated the suction force that drives the filtration process. A rotary evaporator (Strike-202 Steroglass, Italy) set at 78 °C was used to concentrate the filtrate to dryness.

Fig. 1. Fresh leaves and flower of *P. quercifolium* (Pictures by Muhali Jimoh).

2.3. HPLC-DAD analysis

The profiling of the *P. quercifolium* extract was initially carried out using an HPLC-DAD: Agilent 1200 series USA. The analysis was performed during profiling using an RP-18 HS C18 discovery column (150 mm x 4.6 mm i.d.; 5 μ m, column temperature: room temperature). A mobile phase constituted from 0.1 % trifluoroacetic acid (A) and 0.1 % trifluoroacetic acid (B) respectively dissolved in water and MeOH, at 1 mL/min flow rate was used. After 25 min of programming, the gradient elution transits from 0 min 100 % A to 100 % B. The run was monitored at three detection wavelengths taken at 360, 320 and 280 nm UV channels with an injection volume of 20 μ L.

2.3.1. Ultra-performance liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (UPLC-MS) analysis

The high-resolution UPLC-MS comprised Waters Acquity ultra-performance liquid chromatograph (UPLC) connected to a Waters Synapt G2 Quadrupole time-of-flight (QTOF) mass spectrometer (MS) (Waters, Milford, MA, USA). Electrospray ionisation was used in positive and negative ion modes with a desolvation temperature of 275 $^{\circ}$ C, desolvation gas at 650 L/h, cone voltage of 15 V, and the rest of the MS settings optimised for sensitivity and best resolution. Data were acquired by scanning from m/z 150 to 1500 m/z in resolution mode and MS^E mode.

The two channels of MS data in MS^E mode were obtained at a low collision energy (4 V) and using a collision energy ramp (40–100 V) to get the fragmentation. For accurate mass determination, the instrument was calibrated with sodium formate, and leucine enkephalin was used as reference mass. Separation was achieved on a Waters HSS T3, 2.1 \times 100 mm, 1.7 μ m column. An injection volume of 2 μ L was used and the mobile phase consisted of 0.1 % formic acid (solvent A) and acetonitrile containing 0.1 % formic acid as solvent B. The gradient started at 100 % solvent A for 1 min and changed to 28 % B over 22 min linearly. It then went to 40 % B over 50 s and a wash step of 1.5 min at 100 % B, followed

by re-equilibration to initial conditions for 4 min. The flow rate was 0.3 mL/min and the column temperature was maintained at 55 $^{\circ}$ C. Column Waters BEH C18, 2.1 \times 100 mm, 1.7 μ m, both solvent lines contained 0.1 % formic acid.

2.3.2. Analysis of data under MS^E acquisition mode and sensitivity

The retention time (RT) range was 0.0 - 15.0 min and had a tolerance of \pm 0.2 min. The mass range was 40 - 1200 Da and the mass accuracy tolerance was set at \pm 5 ppm. The adducts $[M + H]^+$, $[M + H - H_2O]^+$, $[M + Na]^+$, $[M + 2H]^{2+}$, $[2M + H]^+$, $[M + H - 2H_2O]^+$, $[M + H - NH_3]^+$, $[M + NH_4]^+$, $[M - H + 2Na]^+$, $[M + K]^+$, $[M + H + K]^{2+}$, $[M + H + Na]^{2+}$, $[M + 2Na]^{2+}$, $[M - 2H + 3Na]^+$ were sorted in positive ion mode while $[M - H]^-$, $[M - 2H]^{2-}$, $[M - H - H_2O]^-$, $[M + Cl]^-$, $[M - H - CO_2]^-$, $[M + HCO_2]^-$, $[2M - H]^-$, were selected in negative ion mode. The data was acquired and processed with MassLynxTM software version 4.1 (Waters, Milford, MA, USA) and the Databridge in MassLynxTM was used to convert the sourced data from project files (.PRO) to NetCDF files (.CDF), and imported subsequently into MZmine for data processing. The m/z tolerance was moderated to 0.01 or 10 ppm.

Unknown compounds were predicted from the RT, MS1 and MS2 (m/z) data for each mode. To identify the metabolites, spectra were selected by aligning the retention times (Table 1) to detect and group unknown compounds, and mark the background compounds. Predictions of the composition were carried out to constrain the thousands of possible candidate structures using the N-rule and seven heuristic rules including restrictions for the number of elements, LEWIS and SENIOR chemical rules, isotopic patterns, hydrogen/carbon ratios, element ratio of nitrogen, oxygen, phosphorus, and sulphur versus carbon, element ratio probabilities and presence of trimethylsilylated compounds. Unknown metabolites were given names based on accurate mass match by matching and linking the masses to Metlin (<http://metlin.scripps.edu/index.php>), MassBank (<http://www.MassBank.jp/http://MassBank.normandata.eu/>), NIST (<http://chemdata.nist.gov/>), and ReSpec (<http://spectra.psc.riken.jp/>). Compounds with accurate mass error

Table 1UPLC-MS, T-MS of compounds identified from leaves of *P. quercifolium* showing retention time, peak area, and biological properties.

No	t _R (min)	MF	UV λ _{max} (nm)	m/z	MS/MS	Tentative name	Reference
1	0.60	C ₉ H ₆ O ₄		177.0072*	161, 163, 147, 131	5-methyl-7-hydroxycoumarin	(Yang et al., 2013)
2	0.72	C ₉ H ₆ O ₂		149.0089	103, 97, 87	Cinnamic acid	ResPect database
3	0.93	C ₇ H ₁₀ O ₅		173.0453	97, 93, 111	Shikimic acid	MassBank
4	1.70	C ₉ H ₁₁ NO ₃		182.0811*	165, 136, 149	Tyrosine	ResPect database, MassBank
5	2.50	C ₉ H ₁₁ NO ₂		166.0859*	120	Phenylalanine	Hokkanen et al., 2009
6	2.60	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ O ₈	271	315.0707	209, 152, 305, 108	Protocatechuic acid 4-O-β-hexoside	Abu-Reidah et al., 2013
7	2.90	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₈	272	299.1128	203, 119	Salicylic acid O-hexoside	Abu-Reidah et al., 2013
8	2.90	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂	272	205.0959	188,	Tryptophan	
9	3.34	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ O ₈	281	327.1076	165	Dihydro-p-coumaric acid hexoside	Fu et al., 2010, Hokkanen et al., 2009
10	3.46	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ O ₈	272	327.1079	147, 165, 191, 103	Dihydro-p-coumaric acid hexoside	Hokkanen et al., 2009
11	3.60	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₁₃	267, 329, 346	479.0816	316, 327, 463, 381	6-Hydroxyquercetin-7-O-β-glucopyranoside	NIST
12	3.70	C ₂₆ H ₂₇ O ₁₅	266, 355	595.1317	479, 300, 316, 327, 205, 101, 161	Quercetin pentosylhexoside	Metlin, NIST
13	3.90	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₁₂	266, 348	463.0880	316, 300, 301	Quercetin-3-O-galactoside	Metlin
14	4.00	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₇	266, 348	303.0508*	153, 229	Quercetin	Tsimogiannis et al., 2007
15	4.20	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₁₁	255, 353	433.0768	300, 301, 383, 271, 284, 255	Quercetin pentoside	Metlin, Tsimogiannis et al., 2007
16	4.30	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₁₁	256, 354	447.0941	301, 151	Quercetin-3-O-rhamnoside	Tsimogiannis et al., 2007
	4.30	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₇	256, 354	303.0505*	177	Quercetin-3-O-rhamnoside	Metlin
17	4.50	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₁₁	267	435.2232	417, 415, 183, 300, 285	Quercetin-3-O-arabinside	Metlin, Tsimogiannis et al., 2007
18	4.50	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₄		211.1695 ^{Li}	193, 175, 133	Scopoletin	Yang et al., 2010
19	4.80	C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₃	281	165.0553	149, 123, 105	Dihydro-p-coumaric acid	ResPect database
20	5.10	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ O ₁₃	267	505.2294	285, 331, 301, 163, 235, 325, 495, 491, 235, 411, 367	Quercetin 3-O-(6'-acetyl-glucoside)	Tsimogiannis et al., 2007
21	5.40	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₇	267	315.0504	300, 301, 271, 165, 255	Isorhamnetin	Tsimogiannis et al., 2007
	5.40	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₇	267	317.0656*	302, 301, 273, 245	Isorhamnetin	Tsimogiannis et al., 2007
22	5.50	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ O ₈	266, 355	345.0597	330, 300, 301, 315, 287, 151, 272	Trimethylquercetin	
	5.50	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ O ₈	266, 355	347.0767*	317, 153, 272	Trimethylquercetin	
23	5.80	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₆	267, 346	299.0544	284, 151, 269	Chrysoeriol (3 ¹ -O-methyluteolin)	Metlin, NIST
	5.80	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₆	267, 346	301.0708*	203, 153	5,7,4'-trihydroxy-3'-methoxyflavone	Metlin, NIST
24	5.90	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₆	267, 346	301.0712*	264, 279	5,7,4'-trihydroxy-3'-methoxyflavone	Metlin, NIST
	6.00	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₆	266, 346	299.0543	284	5,7,4'-trihydroxy-3'-Methoxyflavone isomer	Metlin, NIST
25	6.10	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₇	253, 354	329.0651	314, 299, 271, 315	Tricin	NIST
	6.10	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₇	253, 354	331.0809*	316, 301, 273, 217	Tricin	NIST
26	6.40	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₇	265, 348	359.0756	345, 329, 299, 273, 163	Dimethyl triclin	
	6.40	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₇	265, 348	361.0930*	331, 347, 242	Dimethyl triclin	
27	6.70	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₇	260, 335	329.0652	314, 315	Tricin	
28	6.80	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₇	260, 335	359.0655	344, 329, 313, 163	Dimethyl triclin isomer	
	6.80	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₇	260, 335	361.0916*	300, 331, 272, 167, 329	Dimethyl triclin isomer	
29	7.20	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₆	267, 346	313.0700	298, 283, 255, 270	3 ¹ ,4 ¹ -dimethyluteolin	Metlin, NIST
	7.20	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₆	267, 346	315.0860*	300, 272, 243	3 ¹ ,4 ¹ -dimethyluteolin	Metlin, NIST
30	7.30	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₆	268, 346	313.0713	298, 283, 255	3 ¹ ,4 ¹ -dimethyluteolin isomer	Metlin, NIST
	7.30	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₆	268, 346	315.0860*	300, 272	3 ¹ ,4 ¹ -dimethyluteolin isomer	Metlin, NIST
31	7.40	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₆	266, 346	343.0816	328, 313, 298, 283	3',4',5,7-tetramethoxyfluteolin (methlut)	Metlin, NIST
	7.40	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₆	266, 346	345.0963*	330, 315, 287, 231	3',4',5,7-tetramethoxyfluteolin	Metlin, NIST
32	7.70	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ O ₇		373.0922	343	Trimethyl triclin	
	7.50	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ O ₇		375.1071*	345	Trimethyl triclin	
33	7.90	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₆	268, 346	329.1024*	313, 285	7 methyl-3 ¹ ,4 ¹ -dimethyluteolin	
34	8.00	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ O ₃	268, 346	339.2516	279, 209, 184, 128	Caffeoyl-D-glucose	(Jaiswal et al., 2014; Shakya & Navarre, 2006)
35	8.20	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₇		359.1126*	329, 301, 344	Dimethyl triclin	
36	8.70	C ₁₇ H ₂₈ O ₁₁	268, 346	407.2408	379, 283, 347, 243	Luteolin derivative	
37	8.80	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₆	268, 346	299.2011	299, 271	3 ¹ -O-methyluteolin isomer	MassBank
38	9.10	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₁₁		449.2509	359, 329, 339, 311, 283, 285	aspalalinin (cyclic dihydrochalcone C-glucoside of luteolin)	Stander et al., 2017
39	9.40	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₆		283.2049	255, 93	Luteolin	Metlin, NIST
40	10.00	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₁₃		491.2649	431, 60	Naringenin-6-C-deoxyhexoside pentoside	
41	10.00	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ O ₁₀		433.2572*	373, 313	Naringenin-6-C-glucoside	Metlin, NIST
42	10.20	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₁₀		391.2470	331, 249	Naringenin-6-C-hexoside derivative	
43	10.70	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ O ₁₀		433.2572	373, 141, 391	Naringenin-6-C-hexoside derivative	
44	10.70	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ O ₁₀		457.2566 ^{Na}	373, 315, 297	Naringenin-6-C-glucoside	
45	10.80	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₅		273.2578*	149, 163	Naringenin	MassBank

Results are presented as P06 (PQ)- *Pelargonium quercifolium*. No asteric= m/z in [M-H]⁻ negative ion mode. *= m/z in [M+H]⁺ and ^{Na}[M+Na]⁺ for positive ion mode.

(AME) above 5 were considered unidentified (Zubarev & Makarov, 2013). In addition, unknown compounds were also assigned names based on the number of carbon atoms in the peak and availability of isotope abundances. The accuracy of the annotations was enhanced with the predicted number of carbon atoms in the putatively identified

compounds. Also, the mass fragmentation patterns of the compounds where available in the database were compared and considered. Various phenolic standards like caffeic acid, phloridzin, catechin, rutin, ferulic acid, were also analysed with the samples under the same LC-MS conditions. Their fragmentation patterns were compared to identify

compounds based on the retention times, ionization modes, and mass fragmentation. The recovery test was done by adding the known amounts of standards at low (50 % of the known amounts), medium (same as the known amounts) and high (150 % of the known amounts) levels into samples to evaluate the accuracy of the method. This was applied in triplicate.

2.4. The cytotoxicity of the plant extracts

2.4.1. MTT assay

The cytotoxicity of the ethanolic extract of powdered leaves of *P. quercifolium* tested on TZM-bl cell lines was assessed using the MTT (3-[4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl]-25 diphenyl tetrazolium bromide) cell proliferation assay kit produced by Thermo Fisher Scientific (Johannesburg, South Africa) following the manufacturer's procedure (Palshetkar et al., 2020). Precisely, 10,000 TZM-bl cells were plated in a 96-flat bottom culture plate (Costar) and incubated at 37 °C, 5 % CO₂ for 48 h. Ten microliters of the plant's extract were diluted serially into 10-fold dilutions in a 96-well plate DMEM containing 50 µg/mL Gentamycin, 25 mM Hepes buffer, and 10 % heat-inactivated fetal bovine serum. Uninfected cells were used as the negative control, and the positive control was 30 µg/mL azidothymidine (AZT). Afterwards, a volume of 10 µL MTT reagent (5 mg/mL in PBS) was dispensed in each well and allowed to incubate for 4 h. Thereafter, the AZT medium was swapped with a fresh DMEM (50 µg/mL Gentamycin, 25 mM Hepes buffer, and 10 % heat-inactivated fetal bovine serum) medium. The formazan crystals were dissolved in 50 µL 0.2 % DMSO and subjected to 10 min incubation. A Victor Nivo multimode plate reader (PerkinElmer Inc. USA) was used to measure the absorbance at 540 nm (Nzimande et al., 2022) while a GraphPad Prism Software (v.5.00.288) was used to determine the 50 % cytotoxicity concentration (CC₅₀) for each extract based on the non-fit regression curve. The results were expressed as the percentage viability of cells calculated using the formula:

$$\% \text{ Cell Viability} = \frac{(\text{Sample absorbance} - \text{Cell-free sample blank})}{(\text{Mean media control absorbance})} \times 100$$

2.4.2. Mammalian cell culture and xCELLigence protocol

The HeLa cervical cancer cell model was used to determine the cytotoxicity of the extracts. Briefly, cultures were maintained in 75 cm³ flasks (TPP, Switzerland) in a basal medium consisting of Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (High Glucose), 10 % (v/v) Foetal Calf Serum and 1X antimycotic-antibiotic solution (all available from Gibco). Cultures were evaluated for *Mycoplasma* contamination using standard Hoechst 33,342 staining and fluorescence microscopy. Subculturing was performed using standard trypsinisation and trypan blue enumeration (Filetti et al., 2020). Cells were incubated in a humidified 5 % CO₂ atmosphere kept at 37 °C.

Extract cytotoxicity was evaluated using Electric Cell-Substrate Impedance Sensing (ECIS) on an xCELLigence Real-Time Cell Analyser Single Plate system (RTCA-SP) following solubilisation in 100 % (v/v) dimethylsulfoxide (Sigma-Aldrich, St Louis) and centrifugation at 10 000 rpm to precipitate insoluble mass. Serial dilutions (5 % to 0.08 %) were prepared in basal medium before extract addition following 24-hour cell settling and proliferation. Briefly, 50 µL of warmed basal medium was added to all wells for pre-equilibration and cells were enumerated and added at 20,000 cells per well in 100 µL volume. Extracts were prepared at a 4:1 ratio to ensure appropriate dilution upon the addition of 50 µL. Effects of extracts were monitored for a further 24 to 48 h of incubation. Cell index values were collected in 15-minute increments. All ECIS runs were performed in E-Plate 96 plates (Agilent) in triplicate wells per extract dilution. Cytotoxicity was determined as Cell Index at a specific time post-dose and calculated using the Sigmoidal Dose Response (Variable Slope). Cell Index vs Time plots were prepared using Graphpad Prism (v9).

2.5. Antiviral screening of plant crude extracts using a luciferase-based antiviral assay

The JC. 53 cells were first used to generate the TZM-bl cells used in this experiment by inserting distinct integrated copies of the luciferase gene under the control of the HIV-1 promoter (Sarzotti-Kelsoe et al., 2014). The TZM-bl cells were maintained at 37 °C and 5 % CO₂ in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) made of 50 µg/mL Gentamycin, 25 mM Hepes buffer and 10 % heat-inactivated fetal bovine serum (Naarding et al., 2014; Sarzotti-Kelsoe et al., 2014).

To achieve graded plant extract concentrations, 10 µL volume each of a 300 µg/mL crude extract in DMEM was diluted 10-fold in a 96-well plate. In the same plate, wells with cells only were plated as negative cell control (CC) and wells with cells and virus only were plated as virus control (VC). After that, 50 µL HIV-1 NL4.3 virus (400 TCID) was added to all wells excluding the cell control wells, and incubated for 1 hour at 37 °C, 5 % CO₂. Then, TZM-bl cell suspension prepared at a density of 10 000 cells/mL in DMEM containing Dextran (Thermo Fisher, South Africa) was seeded (10 000 cells/well) in a 96-well plate (Costar) and incubated at 37 °C, 5 % CO₂ for 72 h. A positive control was set up using azidothymidine (AZT), a known reverse transcriptase inhibitor at a starting concentration of 30 µg/mL, which was also included in the experiment (virus control). After incubation, the DMEM medium was swapped, and 100 µL BrightGlo luciferase reagent (Promega, Madison, United States) was added to each well under low light conditions and incubated at room temperature for 2 min to allow complete cell lysis. All the contents were transferred to a corresponding 96-well bottom flat black plate (Costar, Germany). Luminescence was measured at 540 nm in a Victor Nivo multimode microplate reader (PerkinElmer; USA) immediately. The viral replication level was determined as a percentage of the HIV-1 inhibition using the following equation:

$$\% \text{ HIV inhibition} = \frac{(\text{Average sample} - \text{Average control})}{[1 - (\text{Average viral control} - \text{Average control})]} \times 100$$

The 50 % cytotoxicity concentration (IC₅₀) for each extract was calculated from a GraphPad Prism Software (v.5.00.288) based on the non-fit regression curve.

2.6. Full feed analysis

Nutritional properties vis-à-vis macronutrients, micronutrients and proximate materials in the pulverised leaves of *P. quercifolium* were determined following the AOAC (2016)'s referenced methods. The mineral composition of the tested samples was analysed using the Inductively Coupled Plasma- Optical Emission Spectrometer (Varian Vista-MPX, Victoria 3170, Australia) available in the Analytical laboratory of the Department of Agriculture, Kwa-Zulu Natal, South Africa.

3. Results

3.1. HPLC DAD and UPLC-QTOF-MS quantitation of phenolic compounds

The UV/vis absorption is a primary means of quantifying phenolic compounds. This method can be employed to distinguish among subclasses of phenolic compounds. Generally, researchers use the aglycone standard for many of the glycosylated forms, especially for O-linked compounds because glycosylation does not affect the absorption coefficients of the compounds and the optimum absorption wavelengths. After all, the glycosidic and alkyl residues are poor chromophores (Simirgiotis et al., 2009). However, this is different for C-linked glycosides which can establish a new series of conjugated bonds and significantly alter the absorption spectra although C-linked glycosides are rare. For the qualitative analysis, five chemical markers were employed for simultaneous quantitative determination. These include, caffeic acid

(2), ferulic acid (5) and coumaric acid (4); one flavanol (6) one dihydrochalcone (8), one flavanone (7) and two flavano-3-ols (1/3). These metabolites were the most abundant in the extracts. The ultra-violet detection wavelengths were chosen based on the UV spectrum of the markers. At 300, 309 and 322 nm, phenolic acids had most vital UV absorption whereas flavanones (284, 330 nm), flavanols (254, 255 and 354 nm), dihydrochalcones (284 nm) and flavan-3-ol (278 nm) had the indicated UV absorption. Using the methods described, the phenolic compounds were detectable and quantifiable in extracts of *P. quercifolium* (Table 2) sampled with a high degree of sensitivity, as indicated by their limits of quantification and detection (Table 3). The suitability of this method for profiling phenolic compounds from the tested samples was supported by the limits of detection and quantification observed coupled with the calculated recoveries. Many papers have reported quantifying phenolic compounds using HPLC-DAD and UHPLC-MS and expressed as ferulic acid, caffeic acid, hesperidin, coumaric acid, epicatechin, rutin catechin, or other phenolic compounds equivalents.

3.2. Identification of phenolic acids and their derivatives and other metabolites

(a) Hydroxybenzoic acids: Peak 6 and 7 represented hydroxybenzoic acid peaks identified from *P. quercifolium* extract (Fig. 2). Peak 6 was tentatively identified as protocatechuic acid 4-O- β -hexoside after displaying [M-H]⁻ ion at *m/z* 315 with main fragments, *m/z* 152 [M-H-162]⁻, 108 [M-H-CO₂]⁻ upon collision inductive dissociation (CID) as reported by Fu et al. (2010). Fragmentation in Peak 7 belonged to that of salicylic acid O-hexoside when compared to that of literature (Abu-Reidah et al., 2013).

(b) Hydroxycinnamic acids: Six hydroxycinnamic acids were detected at peaks 2, 4, 9, 10, 19, and 34. Peak 2 (*m/z* 147) was identified as that of free cinnamic acid following loss of 44 Da due to carbon dioxide. While the ion at *m/z* 87 also corresponds with cinnamic acid [cinnamic acid -H-CO₂-OH]⁻. The ions at *m/z* 179, 161, and 135, for

peak 4, suggest the presence of a caffeoyl and are thus identified as caffeic acid typical of fragmentation of the reference standard (Fig. 2). The peaks 9 and 10 were tentatively identified as dihydro-p-coumaric acid hexoside with *m/z* 327 ([M-H]⁻) and major fragments; *m/z* 147 for cinnamoyl moiety or *m/z* 147[dihydrocoumaroyl-H-H₂O]⁻, *m/z* 165 [dihydro-p-coumaric acid -H]⁻, 191 [M-H-126]⁻ and the ion at *m/z* 103 [cinnamoyl-H-CO₂]⁻. The dihydro-p-coumaric acid was shown at peak 19, *m/z* 165 [dihydro-p-coumaric acid -H]⁻ while peak 34, *m/z* 339, belonged to that of caffeoyl hexose isomer; caffeoyl-D-glucose identified with aid of the literature (Shakya & Navarre, 2006).

3.3. Identification of flavonoids

(a) Flavones: Flavones were the most abundant flavonoids represented at peaks 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 35, 36, 37, and 39. The ultraviolet spectrum maxima at 267 and 346 nm, with two hydroxyl groups at the ring B were characteristic of flavones. Peaks 23, 24 and 37 having precursor ion at *m/z* 299, were identified as 3¹-O-methyl luteolin. The MS² fragment, *m/z* 284 [luteolin-H]⁻, formed after the loss of the methyl group, shows a luteolin nucleus. The luteolin itself was detected in peak 39. The fragment *m/z* 151 was due to C-ring degradation by fission of the 1,3 bond to produce the deprotonated molecule's RDA fragment [1,3A-] (Tsimogiannis et al., 2007). Fragments; *m/z* 269 [M-H-H₂O]⁻, *m/z* 272 [M-H-CO]⁻, *m/z* 119 (formed due to [M-H-H₂O]⁻ followed by [1,3B]⁻ (C-ring fission) were also formed. Peaks 29 and 30 showed precursor ion 3¹-O-methyl luteolin ions at *m/z* 313 [M - H]⁻ were identified as 3¹,4¹-dimethyl luteolin after showing extra methyl group to 3¹-O-methyl luteolin with *m/z* 313 consistent with the literature (Kuwabara et al., 2003). Peaks 23 exhibited precursor ion at *m/z* 329 and was identified as 7 methyl-3¹,4¹-dimethyl luteolin showing extra methylation of 3¹,4¹-dimethyl luteolin. Further methylation formed 3',4',5,7-tetramethoxyluteolin (methlut) at peak 31 identified in both negative and positive ion modes. Peak 36 with precursor ions *m/z* 407 was identified as a derivative of luteolin due to fragment ion for luteolin nucleus at *m/z* 284 and uv absorption at 268, 346 nm. Peaks 25 and 27

Table 2

The amount of phenolic compounds quantitated from *P. quercifolium* extract.

Phenolic Subclass	Phenolic Compound	Amount	Phenolic Subclass	Phenolic Compound	Amount
Hydroxybenzoic acids (mg/L CoAE)	Protocatechuic acid 4-O- β -hexoside	23.2 \pm 0.0	Flavonols (mg/L (RE))	6-Hydroxyquercetin-7-O- β -glucopyranoside	8.2 \pm 0.0
	Salicylic acid O-hexoside	45.6 \pm 0.0		Quercetin pentosylhexoside	6.7 \pm 0.0
	Total	68.8 \pm 15.8		Quercetin-3-O-galactoside	35.3 \pm 0.0
Hydroxycinnamic acids (mg/L CoAE/ CAE)	Cinnamic acid	32.8 \pm 0.0		Quercetin	112.1 \pm 36.4
	Caffeic acid	35.5 \pm 0.0		Quercetin pentoside	18.9 \pm 0.0
	p-coumaric acid	60.0 \pm 0.0		Quercetin-3-O-rhamnoside	44.8 \pm 0.0
	Dihydro-p-coumaric acid hexoside	94.6 \pm 15.8		Quercetin-3-O-arabinoside	20.6 \pm 0.0
	Caffeoyl-D-glucose	13.3 \pm 0.0		Quercetin 3-O-(6'-acetyl-glucoside)	8.5 \pm 0.0
	Total	236.9 \pm 31.2		Isorhamnetin	50.9 \pm 9.8
Flavones (mg/L (HE))	3 ¹ -O-methyl luteolin	104.8 \pm 23.2		Trimethylquercetin	86.4 \pm 32.4
	Tricin	371.8 \pm 223.6		Total	409.2 \pm 35.7
	Dimethyl triclin	727.6 \pm 20.1		Naringenin-6-C-deoxyhexoside pentoside*	61.3 \pm 0.0
	3 ¹ ,4 ¹ -dimethyl luteolin	276.8 \pm 62.5		Naringenin-6-C-glucoside*	393.2 \pm 0.0
	3',4',5,7-tetramethyl luteolin	557.0 \pm 323.2		Naringenin-6-C-hexoside derivative*	98.2 \pm 41.7
	Trimethyl triclin	638.9 \pm 389.2		Naringenin-6-C-glucoside*	155.6 \pm 0.0
	7 methyl-3 ¹ ,4 ¹ -dimethyl luteolin	393.2 \pm 0.0	Naringenin	196.6 \pm 0.0	
	Luteolin derivative	22.9 \pm 0.0	Total	904.9 \pm 129.5	
	Luteolin	44.2 \pm 0.0	Aspalalinin*	5.2 \pm 0.0	
	Total	3191.1 \pm 253.3	Dihydrochalcone (mg/L (PE))	Total	5.2 \pm 0.0

Data expressed as mean \pm SD; CE = Catechin equivalents, CAE = caffeic acid equivalent, CoAE = coumaric acid equivalent, RE = rutin equivalent, HE = hesperidin equivalent, PE = Phloridzin equivalent.

* Assumption: absorption spectra were not altered.

Table 3

LOD and LOQ values calculated for standard phenolic compounds.

No	Name	t _R (min)	UV _{λmax} (nm)	m/z (M-H) ⁻	m/z MS/MS	Regression equation	Linear range mg/L	R ²	LOD mg/L	LOQ mg/L
1	Catechin	8.7	278	289	289, 245, 205, 137, 109	y = 1163.4x	3.9–31.3	0.999	1.7	5.8
2	Caffeic acid	9.4	300, 322	179	179, 135	y = 703.7x + 20.9	3.9–31.3	1.000	2.9	9.5
3	Epicatechin	10.8	278	289	289, 245, 205, 137, 109	y = 1553.3x + 938.1	3.9–31.3	0.998	1.3	4.3
4	p-coumaric acid	11.8	300, 309	163	163, 119	y = 625.1x - 516.0	3.9–31.3	1.000	3.2	10.7
5	Ferulic acid	13.4	300, 322	193	193, 179, 149, 134	y = 487.8x - 57.7	3.9–31.3	0.997	4.1	13.7
6	Rutin	14.5	254, 255, 354	609	609, 301	y = 1155.5x + 205.9	3.9–31.3	0.998	1.7	5.8
7	Hesperidin	17.4	284, 330	609	608, 301	y = 610.4x + 7.9	3.9–31.3	0.994	3.3	11.0
8	Phloridzin	17.9	284	435	435, 273, 167	y = 1308.6x + 1603.3	3.9–15.6	1.000	1.5	5.1

Flavanols were quantified against catechin and thus expressed as catechin equivalents, flavanones were expressed as hesperidin equivalents, flavonols were expressed as quercetin equivalents, while dihydrochalcones were expressed as phloridzin equivalents.

Fig. 2. UHPLC-ESI-MS base peak chromatogram for aqueous (A) and 70 % ethanol (B) extracts of *P. quercifolium* cultivars analysed in the ESI -ve and ESI +ve modes.

showed precursor ion at m/z 329 [tricin-H]⁻, with fragments m/z 315 [M-H-CH₃]⁻, 299 [M-H-2CH₃]⁻, and 271 [M-H-2CH₃-CO]⁻. Peaks 26, 28 and 35 were identified from the precursor ion m/z 359 as dimethyl tricrin—the MS² fragment; m/z 345 [tricin-H+CH₃]⁻, formed after loss of a methyl. Further methylation of dimethyl tricrin could develop trimethyl tricrin as noted at peak 32.

(b) Dihydrochalcone: Dihydrochalcone in *P. quercifolium* extract was identified at peak 38 as a cyclic dihydrochalcone C-glucoside of luteolin because it exhibited similar fragments to those in the previously identified samples by Stander et al. (2017).

(c) Flavonols: This group of compounds showed strong ultra-violet

absorptions at 266, 348 and 355 nm. Ten peaks were identified as belonging to those of flavonols (peaks: 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 20, 21, and 22) in the *P. quercifolium* extract. Peak 11 with precursor ion m/z 479 was identified as 6-hydroxyquercetin-7-O-β-glucopyranoside with the characteristic hydroxyquercetin (Quercetagenin) aglycone ion having fragments m/z 316. The ion at 463 was due to loss of OH, thus representing quercetin-7-O-β-glucopyranoside. Peaks 14, 16, and 22 were identified to be those of quercetin; [quercetin+H]⁺; m/z 303 with common MS² fragments 229 [quercetin+H-CHO-OH-CO]⁺ and 153 [^{1,3}A⁺], formed through retrocyclization cleavages of the C-ring of the aglycone involving 1 and 3 bonds (bonds 1 and 3 refer to the O—C-2 and

C-3-C-4 bonds of the C-ring with intact A ring) (Tsimogiannis et al., 2007) or trimethyl quercetin (peak 22) showing consecutive loss of methyl groups at m/z 330, 315, 301, and the fragment 287 [quercetin-H-OH]⁻, and 151 [^{1,3}A]⁻. Quercetin aglycone underwent sugar conjugation to form quercetin-3-O-pentosylhexoside in negative ion mode. Also, quercetin-3-O-galactoside at peak 13 was formed by adding a galactose (162 Da). The addition of pentoside sugar, rhamnoside, and arabinoside to quercetin was noted at peaks 15, 16 and 17, respectively. Conjugation with acetyl glucoside (204 Da) (peak 19) formed quercetin-3-O-acetyl glucoside. Peaks 21 and 40 were identified as isorhamnetin and isorhamnetin 4'-O-glucuronide respectively. Isorhamnetin displayed characteristic fragment ions; m/z 315 [isorhamnetin -H]⁻, m/z 301 [isorhamnetin - H- CH₃]⁻, m/z 271 [M-H-CH₃-CO]⁻, m/z 165 [^{0,2}A]⁻, and m/z 255 [M-H-H₂O-CO]⁻. Conjugation with glucuronide formed isorhamnetin 4'-O-glucuronide with precursor ion m/z 491, [M-H]⁻.

(d) Flavanones: Six chromatographic peaks (40, 41, 42, 43, 44 and 45) from *P. quercifolium* extract were considered to have a flavanone skeleton. Naringenin exhibited precursor ion of m/z 273 [naringenin +H]⁺ at peak 45 with MS² fragments m/z 163 [^{0,4}B]⁺, as main fragment formed through retrocyclization cleavages of the C-ring of naringenin involving 0 and 4 bonds (bonds 0 and 4 refer to the O—C-1 and C-3—C-4 bonds of the C-ring) (Tsimogiannis et al., 2007). The other fragment was m/z 149 [^{1,3}A]⁺. Naringenin also existed as C-type flavanone glucoside i. e. naringenin-6-C-glucoside or its derivative at peaks 41, 42, 43 and 44 exhibiting non-homogenous cleavages owing to loss of 120 and 90 amu in C-hexoses arising from cross ring at 0,2 and 0,3 cleavages of the sugar moieties versus 104 and 74 amu in C-deoxyhexosides and 90 and 60 amu in C-pentosides. [^{0,2}B]⁻ led to the formation of m/z 313 and 151/153 ions, while [0,3B-] could form m/z 297/299 fragments. Naringenin-6-C-deoxyhexoside pentoside was identified at peak 40 with precursor ion m/z 491. Loss of 60 amu gave m/z 431 while [M-H- naringenin- deoxyhexoside]⁻ could provide 132 amu.

3.4. Identification of other compounds

(a) Coumarins: Coumarins were detected at peaks 1, 8, and 18, most of which exhibited characteristic UV λ_{\max} at about 274 nm. Peak 1 belonged to a methylhydroxyl derivative of coumarin through the addition of more of the 14 Da and 17 Da for methyl and hydroxyl respectively. Acetyl hydroxyl derivative (peak 8) was detected too. Peak 18 was tentatively identified as scopoletin via its lithium adduct in the positive ion mode with MS² of characteristic ion, m/z 193 [M + H]⁺, 175 [M + H- OH]⁺ and 133 [M + H-OCH₃ -OH-O]⁺.

(b) Alkaloid: Based on a molecular ion peak [M + H]⁺ at m/z 182.0820 (calcd 182.0812) and a fragment ion at m/z 165.0553 which was formed by the loss of NH₃, Peak 4 was identified as tyrosine. Also, Peak 8 was established as tryptophan, based on a molecular ion peak [M + H]⁺ at m/z 205.0981 (calcd 205.0972). In addition, its MS/MS spectrum displayed a fragment ion [M + H+ NH₃]⁺ at m/z 188.0715 (calcd 188.0711). The preferential loss of ammonia (NH₃) from the protonated tryptophan has been previously proved as a fragmentation pattern, generating the diagnostic 2-carboxyspiro[cyclopropane-indolium] fragment ion. Other compounds like shikimic acid (a carboxylic acid) and phenylalanine (an amino acid) were eluted at Peaks 3 and 5 after 0.93 and 2.50 min respectively and identified using accurate masses and literature.

3.4.1. Analytical protocol validation

The modified UHPLC-MS method (see Section 2.3.1) used in this study was validated with the limit of detection (LOD), the limit of quantification (LOQ), precision, a linearity curve, and recovery according to the recommendations of the International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) (Branch, 2005). Different concentrations of the standard mixture (250.0, 125.0, 62.5.0, 31.25, 15.63, 7.813, and 3.906 mg/L), which were respectively approximated as 250.0, 125.0, 62.5,

31.3, 15.6, 7.8, and 3.9 mg/L mg/L, were injected for quantification. The peak areas were plotted against the series of standard solution concentrations (mg/L) to check the linearity of the calibration curve and to determine the correlation coefficient using a linear regression model. When $r > 0.99$, the system was adjudged to be linear in all cases. The limit of detection (LOD) and the limit of quantification (LOQ) were calculated by the standard deviation of the response and slope parameters of the analytical curves. The standard deviation of the y-intercepts of regression lines was used as the standard deviation of the blank (Table 3).

The repeatability of *P. quercifolium* samples was assessed variations using interday and intraday variations, and the relative standard deviation (RSD) was taken as a measure of precision. The intraday and interday variations were analysed using six replicates during a single day and by duplicating the experiments on three consecutive days. The percentage relative standard deviations (% RSD) of the peak areas (UV detection) and retention times were determined for each peak detected. The intraday repeatability (expressed as% RSDs) of the retention times ranged from 0.14 to 3.14 %, whereas the interday repeatability was from 1.01 to 2.90 %. The total peak area's intraday repeatability (expressed as % RSDs) was 0.32–0.70 %, whereas the interday repeatability was 1.01–1.13 % (Table 1).

3.5. Cytotoxicity of ethanolic extract of *P. quercifolium*

3.5.1. MTT cells proliferation

The cytotoxicity analysis was performed on TZM-bl cells using MTT proliferation. The cytotoxicity of crude extract of *P. quercifolium* was represented as the percentage of cell viability. Fig. 3 showed the *P. quercifolium*'s extract cell viability of >80 % and the cell cytotoxicity at 50 % was very wide to determine (Fig. 3). According to the United States National Cancer Institute Plant Screening Program, a crude extract is generally considered to have in vitro cytotoxic activity when the CC₅₀ value is <30 - 40 µg/mL (Talib et al., 2010). The cytotoxicity of the extract as obtained from the results indicate that the tested extract of *P. quercifolium* could not be determined as it was very wide. The positive reference, AZT, did not show cytotoxicity on TZM-bl cells at a concentration of 35.64 µg/mL which is equivalent to the CC₅₀ value of the tested plant extract. The significance of the CC₅₀ is paramount to the determination of toxic concentration of the extract, and the exclusion of non-specific antiviral activity.

Fig. 3. Percentage of cell viability of TZM-bl cell lines against *P. quercifolium* extract using the MTT viability assay. Results were obtained from two independent experiments; data represent the mean SEM. P. quercifolium extract showed 80 % cell viability and positive control 100 %. The x-axis shows *P. quercifolium* crude extract, AZT (Zidovudine), SB (sodium butyrate), PQ stands for *P. quercifolium* extract.

$$(\%) \text{Cell Viability} = \frac{(\text{Sample} - \text{Cell-free sample blank})}{(\text{Mean media control absorbance})} \times 100$$

3.5.2. Cytotoxicity of *P. quercifolium* fractions against HeLa cervical cancer cells

Extract cytotoxicity was evaluated through real-time Electric Cell-Substrate Impedance Sensing (ECIS) using the HeLa cervical cancer model to determine relative half-maximal inhibitory constants (IC_{50}) for the fractions. Cells were allowed to settle and grow for 24 h prior to exposure to ethanolic extract of *P. quercifolium*. Overlapping growth curves seen in the initial 24 h of the assay offer a clear indication that cell seeding was equal in each well. Cell growth proceeded as expected prior to exposure to the extracts. As can be seen in Fig. 5, all extracts showed characteristic relative concentration dependencies, i.e. increasing relative concentrations increases the relative toxicity of the extract. The effect of the extracts was monitored following the initial 24 h for cellular proliferation. Large spikes observed at 24 h are artifacts of the removal and replacement of the Eplate into the xCELLigence cradle and do not affect the toxicity monitoring (Fig. 4). Rapid decreases in cell index (CI) values observed at higher extract percentages are highly indicative of cell death as the rapid reduction in electrical impedance measurement is an indication of a decrease in direct contact of the cellular monolayer with the surface; increases in CI represent the inverse of this. Based on the responses observed 48 h post-exposure, the relative IC_{50} values were determined using the area under the curve analysis during this period using the concentration range of 0.16 – 2.5 %. Table 3 shows the calculated IC_{50} values determined for each extract with relative goodness of fit represented by the R^2 value. The plant extract showed high levels of cytotoxicity as determined by the xCELLigence. The potential effect of DMSO on the cytotoxicity cannot be negated although observation of CI vs time for 2.5 % (v/v) DMSO showed little toxicity.

3.6. The anti-HIV-1 activity of the *P. quercifolium* extract

Ethanolic extracts of *P. quercifolium* had significant inhibitory effects on the level of replication of the HIV-1. Fig. 5 describes the dose-response curve of the *P. quercifolium* crude extract (PQ) determining the inhibitory concentration at 50 % (IC_{50}) and the percentage of HIV inhibition. *Pelargonium quercifolium* crude extract showed 100 % HIV-1 inhibition when compared with AZT (positive control). The *P. quercifolium* crude extract's IC_{50} value of 0.009787 mg/mL at which the extract induced the inhibition of at least 50 % of the HIV-1 was considerably low and comparable to the AZT standard (Fig. 5).

3.7. Nutritional composition of *P. quercifolium*

The nutritional composition of tested leaves of *P. quercifolium* is presented in Table 4. Results show that *P. quercifolium* contains an appreciable amount of macronutrients (Ca, K, Mg, Na, P, N),

Fig. 4. Cytotoxicity of fractions of *P. quercifolium* against HeLa cervical cancer cells.

Fig. 5. Dose-response curve showing the anti-HIV-1 activity of the *P. quercifolium* crude extract (Blue) and AZT (red) as the positive control tested in the TZM-bl cell lines. The x-axis shows the serial dilution of crude extract concentrations in Log scale and y-axis shows the percentage of HIV-1 inhibition.

Table 4

Nutritional composition of *P. quercifolium* leaves.

Macroelements (%)		Microelements (ppm)		Proximate content (%)	
Ca	1.71 ± 0.11	Cu	6.00 ± 0.40	ADF	34.08 ± 0.88
K	4.97 ± 0.52	Fe	579.50 ± 58.50	Ash	18.87 ± 0.89
Mg	0.52 ± 0.18	Mn	96.50 ± 7.71	Fat	4.46 ± 0.39
Na	0.79 ± 0.07	Zn	80.00 ± 3.68	NDF	51.53 ± 4.64
P	0.27 ± 0.08			Moisture	9.13 ± 1.37
N	2.53 ± 0.13			Protein	15.82 ± 0.87

macronutrients (Cu, Fe, Mn, Zn) and proximate substances (ADF, ash, fat, NDF, moisture, protein).

4. Discussion

The LC-MS characterization shows that *P. quercifolium* species is a depot of numerous flavonoid and phenolic metabolites such as isorhamnetin, aspalalinin, trimethylquercetin, naringenin, chrysoeriol (3'-o-methyluteolin), tricetin, naringenin-6-c-deoxyhexoside, dimethyl tricetin, naringenin-6-c-hexoside derivative, 3',4'-dimethyluteolin, naringenin-6-c-glucoside, trimethyl tricetin and 7 methyl-3',4'-dimethyluteolin and tryptophan, an alkaloid. Most of these compounds play crucial roles in anticancer, immunomodulation, anti-HIV, antioxidation and anti-inflammation coupled with profound stimulatory and protective effects on the cardiovascular and nervous systems (Gong et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2009; Qin et al., 2011; Stander et al., 2017; Zeng et al., 2018). If advanced to clinical trials, the present and potential pharmacological usage of these chemicals can be optimized given an array of medicinal benefits attributed to their constitutional and conformational synthetic analogues.

Among the natural phenolics, flavonoids are members of a huge subclass of compounds, most of which are well-known inhibitors of several enzymes that are essential for HIV replication, such as RT viral protease and viral enzyme integrase (Li et al., 2014; Pasetto et al., 2014; Wang et al., 1998). The analysis and quantification of phenolic compounds in *P. quercifolium* reveals that flavones were the most detected and quantified subclass of phenolic compounds amounting to 3191.1 ± 253.3 mg/L (HE) followed by flavonones with 904.9 ± 129.5 mg/L (HE) and then flavonols (409.2 ± 35.7 mg/L (RE)) among the flavonoids characterized in the extract of *P. quercifolium*. Phenolic acids (hydroxycinnamic acids and hydroxybenzoic acids) were the least represented. Recently, flavones have been thought of as exhibiting efficient inhibitory effects against HIV, Sar-Cov and other viral diseases (Jo et al., 2020; Zakaryan et al., 2017)

The anti-HIV activities of quercetin and its derivatives have been reviewed (Septembre-Malaterre et al., 2022). Quercetin induces inhibition of syncytium formation and protection of HIV-1 induced cytopathic effects (Di Petrillo et al., 2022). Quercetin demonstrated high inhibitory effects on HIV-1 reverse transcriptase (HIV-1 RT) (RDDP and

DDDP) and HIV-1 IN (HIV-1 integrase) as reported by Khan and Ather (2007) suggesting that quercetin may have been among the cardinal metabolites responsible for the high inhibitory effect of *P. quercifolium* extract on HIV-1. Luteolin itself was recently found to inhibit HIV-1 infection in reporter cells and primary human lymphocytes and displayed antiviral activity in a latent HIV-1 reactivation model and abolished effectively HIV-1Tat-driven long-terminal repeat (LTR) promoter transactivation possibly by interfering with pTEF-b binding with LTR or by abolishing Tat binding altogether (Lu et al., 2023; Mehla et al., 2011). Luteolin may also prevent NF- κ B-activation or inhibit host factors involved in transcription (Mehla et al., 2011). These secondary metabolites may have contributed significantly to the inhibitory effect of the tested *P. quercifolium* on HIV-1 infected cells. Since the tested extract of *P. quercifolium* exerted an inhibitory effect on the HIV-1 infected cells at a low IC₅₀ value of 0.009787 mg/mL (Fig. 4), it is expedient to attribute the extract's efficacy to several antiviral compounds (Table 1) characterised by the LC-MS in the solvent fractions of *P. quercifolium*. The comparable anti-HIV-1 efficacy of the extract to the AZT standard as revealed by this study suggests that *P. quercifolium* is a natural substitute for most synthetic antiretroviral drugs.

The anticancer properties of phenolic compounds have been reported extensively in the literature (Bhattarai et al., 2021; Maheshwari & Sharma, 2023; Roleira et al., 2015). Already, the LC-MS characterization has revealed the diversity of anticancer metabolites in the tested extract of *P. quercifolium*. Hydroxycinnamic acids increased cytotoxicity and apoptosis of DU145 of prostate cancer (Szliszka et al., 2011). Also, p-coumaric acid decreased the number of viable MDA-MB 468 and HBL 100 breast cells, colon-derived SW480 cells and human colonic epithelial cells (Hudson et al., 2000). Kampa et al. (2004) studied the anti-proliferative action of protocatechuic acid on T47D human breast cancer cells. The results showed a time and dose-dependent inhibitory effect on cell growth whereby the antioxidative activity of these phenolic acids in T47D cells does not coincide with their inhibitory effect on tumoral proliferation. Quercetin, by attenuating prostate cancer cell survival, led to the inhibition of antiapoptotic pathways in the human PCa cell lines, LNCaP, DU-145, and PC-3 (Ward et al., 2018). Luteolin through attenuation of epithelial-mesenchymal transition induced by TGF- β 1 in lung cancer cells in the human adenocarcinoma cell line A549 (Chen et al., 2013). Coumarins and its derivatives with potent in vitro/in vivo biological activity were implicated as promising anticancer compounds (Detsi et al., 2017; Kontogiorgis et al., 2012).

The efficacy of the characterised anticancer compounds in the leaf extract of *P. quercifolium* and their synergistic effects in causing the death of mammalian cervical cancer cells was further revealed by the xCELLigence real-time cell analyser where rapid reduction in cell index at higher dosages of the extract within the concentration range of 0.16 - 5 % indicates cell death (Jimoh et al., 2024b). Although the inhibitory mechanism of the tested extract was not established, the apoptosis initiated by the extract of *P. quercifolium* may have resulted from a decline in cell viability occasioned by a drastic reduction in metabolically active cells after treatment with *P. quercifolium* (Nemade et al., 2018). Findings from this study suggest that the extract of *P. quercifolium* has inhibitory effects against cervical cancer in a time and dose-dependent manner as previously reported by Pérez-Sánchez et al. (2019).

The nutrient profile of *P. quercifolium* leaf is sparsely reported in the literature as there is little to no study on the mineral and proximate composition of the species and its close relatives. This has made imperative, the need to investigate its food value to evaluate its edibility and potential use for food fortification. Findings from this study reveal that the nutrient profile of *P. quercifolium* is comparable to most edible vegetables such as *Celosia argentea* L. (Adegbaju et al., 2019), *Spinacea oleracea* L. (Salehi et al., 2018), *Amaranthus caudatus* L. (Jimoh et al., 2020) and numerous wild leafy vegetables (Afolayan & Jimoh, 2009). Also, the mineral and proximate content of *P. quercifolium* is higher than most antiviral and anticancer plants earlier reported (De Clercq, 2005;

Jimoh et al., 2024b; Kohli et al., 2022; Moraes et al., 2017; Zhang et al., 2022) suggesting that its nutrient status and metabolic fingerprints can be harnessed to develop a functional anticancer or antiviral food recipe.

5. Conclusion

This study underpins the potential of the anticancer and antiviral metabolites of *P. quercifolium* as a pharmacological precursor. For the first time, the nutrient profile of *P. quercifolium* was reported coupled with an interesting revelation of its metabolic fingerprints. Further studies may be conducted to investigate the mechanism of action of these metabolites, and their individual and synergistic effects in preventing and curing cancer, HIV-AIDS and other chronic diseases.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Muhali Olaide Jimoh: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Nasifu Ker-ebba:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Olaitan Chinenye Okechukwu:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Abdullahi Adekilekun Jimoh:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Taofeek Salaudeen:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Samuel Oloruntoba Bamigboye:** Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Avela Sogoni:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Kunle Okaiyeto:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Data curation. **Nompumelelo Mkhwanazi:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation. **Rose Kadye:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Oladayo Amed Idris:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Mariana Erasmus:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Earl Prinsloo:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation. **Charles Petrus Laubscher:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Resources, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

All authors wish to state that there is no interest to declare.

Data availability

All data generated or analysed during this study is included in this article.

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